

EVALUATION ON HIGH DAMPING ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR LOW NOISE MATERIAL

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SUMMARY: AIMCs (aluminum matrix composites), reinforced with SiC and graphite particles, have various advantages over conventional materials as well as Al-alloys. Recently, the wear resistance and solid lubricant properties of the particulate reinforced AIMCs were studied. In addition to these properties, graphite and SiC particles can enhance the damping property.

In this study the damping capacity of Al-alloy, Mn-Cu alloy and Al-Si aluminum alloys reinforced with SiC and nickel coated graphite particles at various contents has been investigated. Their mechanical property, and microstructure were also investigated. The loss factor of half power bandwidth of clamped-free cantilever beam specimens was measured over a wide range of resonant frequencies from 50 to 3300Hz in the first three modes of flexure. Al-10%SiC_p-10%C_p shows the highest loss factor at the mode 1 while Mn-Cu alloy showed the highest loss factor at the modes 2 and 3. Consequently, at the mode 1 the Al-10%SiC_p-10%C_p specimen shows the loss factor of 0.00933, which is 2.64 and 1.58 times higher than those of Al-alloy and Mn-Cu alloy, respectively.

KEYWORDS: damping, aluminum, silicon carbide (SiC), graphite, particle, casting

INTRODUCTION

Noise problems are becoming an important issue for working environments as well as in daily life. Especially, commercial and military vessels require highly reduced noise in order to increase their comfort and acoustic stealth. There are many sources of noise but the mechanical parts rotating at high speed are mostly responsible for the noise source. High damping materials may be necessary to reduce the noise of rotating parts with suppression of vibration and dissipation through heat.

The AIMCs reinforced with graphite and SiC particles are being used in the mobile industry [1,2] and the aeronautic industry because of their lightness, wear resistance, and dimensional stability at high temperatures. In addition to these properties, particulate reinforced AIMCs have good damping capacity due to

- i) The dissipation of energy at the interface between the matrix and the reinforcement
- ii) The micro-plastic deformation in ductile reinforcement
- iii) The generation of high dislocation density at the interface resulting from the difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) difference between the matrix and the reinforcement and
- iv) The presence of micro-voids at the interface.

Damping materials can absorb the vibration well and dissipate it as heat. The factors contributing to damping of the AIMCs reinforced with graphite and SiC particles are process, the shape, amount and kind of particles, and heat-treatment [3].

In general, SiC has almost no intrinsic damping capacity, but damping can be enhanced by dislocation as in iii) above-mentioned. SiC has a lower CTE than aluminum such the difference in the CTE makes high shear stress when it is cooled down from the melt. This shear stress at the interface enhances the dislocation density by tens of times. According to the Grant-Lucke

theory, damping is closely related to the dislocation density. The vibration and motion of dislocation reveal high damping capacity by dissipating externally forced stress [4].

Graphite is anisotropic. Graphite has low vertical bonding energy compared to graphen layer. Therefore, it can be micro-plastically deformed by shear stress. During deformation of graphite, the externally forced energy is changed to heat energy by internal friction and graphite reveals excellent intrinsic damping property. Rohatgi et al. found that damping is increased linearly as the extent of incorporated graphite increases [5].

The possible problem in casting the AlMCs is the wettability of reinforcements. Rohatgi et al. coated the surface of graphite with copper to increase the wettability. Another problem is the difference in density between the SiC and graphite. Once they are wetted well by molten aluminum, if left without stirring graphite particles float while SiC particles settle down.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the damping capacity of Al-Si aluminum alloy matrix composites reinforced with SiC and nickel-coated graphite particles at various contents. For comparison, the damping capacity of Al-alloy and Mn-Cu alloy has also been investigated. Their mechanical property and microstructure were also examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials. The ingots used in this study are GrA-Ni 10S4G from INCO and F3S20S from Duralcan. GrA-Ni 10S4G was reinforced with 4vol.% graphite and 10vol.% SiC particles. F3S20S was reinforced with 20vol.% SiC particles. The chemical compositions of each matrix of GrA-Ni 10S4G and F3S20S are given in Table 1. Nickel-coated graphite particle is NOVAMET from INCO. The graphite used is shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1. Chemical compositions of AlMC ingots used (wt.%)

Alloy	Si	Mg	Fe	Mn	Cu	Al
Matrix of GrA-Ni	9.2	0.58	0.16	0.10	0.19	Bal.
Matrix of F3S20S	9.7	0.39	0.81	0.39	-	Bal.

Fig. 1. Microphotograph of nickel-coated graphite.

Method. Four AlMCs were casted using the ingots and nickel-coated graphite particle with investment casting at Chun-ji, Corp. (Seoul, Korea) in a high frequency induction furnace. The casting conditions of the AlMCs were summarized in Table 2. Graphite particles were incorporated with stirring in order to distribute uniformly and the stir-casting process and condition have been reported in detail elsewhere [6,7]. Before and after the particle

incorporation, a nitrogen gas was made to flow on the surface of the molten aluminum, while particle incorporating the RPM of stirrer was strictly controlled in order to prevent from air inflow into the melt.

Microstructure observation was conducted using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JSM-5900, JEOL). The chemical composition was analyzed using Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometer (EDS, INCA Energy 200, Oxford). The mechanical properties were measured using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM, Instron 8801, INSTRON) with a crosshead speed of 0.1m/sec.

Table 2. Reinforcement composition of AIMCs

No.	SiC (vol.%)	Graphite (vol.%)	Casting condition
1	10	4	GrA-Ni 10S4G remelt
2	10	10	GrA-Ni 10S4G remelt + nickel coated graphite
3	20	0	F3S20S remelt
4	20	4	F3S20S remelt + nickel coated graphite

The damping capacity of AIMCs was investigated according to ASTM E756-83. Manganese-copper and aluminum alloy damping specimens were also prepared for comparison. For damping tests, the specimens of 10×2×150mm in size were machined. The damping measurement system is illustrated in Fig. 2. One end of the damping specimen was fixed by a clamp and a non-contact exciter transducer (Bruel and Kjaer (B&K), MM002) vibrated the other end of the specimen. A signal generator induced sine waves and a non-contact pick-up transducer (Bruel and Kjaer (B&K), MM004) picked up the correspondence of the specimen. A Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analyzer (HP 35670A) analyzed the response as a function of frequency.

If a specimen was excited with broadband white noise, the response signal was analyzed using a FFT analyzer. At each resonant frequency, a sine sweep function was used, which measures vibration response against frequency by slowly increasing frequency. Loss factor was measured from the frequency response at each resonant frequency using a half power bandwidth method.

Fig. 2. Damping measurement system.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Microstructure of AlMC reinforced with graphite and SiC particles

The microstructure of the Al-10%SiC_p-4%C_p casted is shown in Fig. 3. Graphite is uniformly distributed. Nickel-coated graphite particles were incorporated well by increasing the wettability to aluminum alloy. The problem due to the density difference was not observed in this AlMC.

Fig. 3. Microphotograph of Al-10%SiC_p-4%C_p after casting.

The EDS analysis was conducted to find out how nickel existed. Fig. 4 shows the result of Al-10%SiC_p-10%C_p. The nickel coated on the surface of graphite was not present on the surface of graphite but dissolved into the matrix. Nickel is of dendrite structure and does not exist in the pure nickel but in the nickel-aluminum precipitate, Al₃Ni, as reported by Ip et al. [7].

Fig. 4. Microphotograph and EDS result after casting Al-10%SiC_p-10%C_p using nickel-coated graphite.

2. Mechanical properties of AlMCs

The mechanical properties were investigated for AlMCs after T6. The tensile strengths are shown in Fig. 5. The tensile strength increases as SiC particles are incorporated.

Fig. 5. Mechanical Properties for Al-alloy and AlMCs.

Fig. 6. Elongation for Al-alloy and AlMCs.

While the tensile strength and the yield strength increase, the elongation decreases with incorporation of SiC and decreased further with incorporation of graphite particle.

3. Damping capacity of AlMCs

A frequency response of Al-10%SiC_p-10%C_p is shown in Fig. 7. It is seen that there are three resonance frequencies from 50 Hz to 3300Hz. Fig. 7 (right) also shows the frequency response at the mode \square . The half power bandwidth of each oscillation mode can be measured with assistance of a sine sweep function, as Fig. 7 (right). The loss factors are measured using a half power bandwidth method as in the equation below.

$$\square = (f_2 - f_1) / f_r$$

where both f_2 and f_1 are the frequencies at half power bandwidth, and f_r is the resonant frequency of the n^{th} mode.

Fig. 7. Frequency response of Al-10SiC_p-10C_p.

The obtained loss factors at each mode are shown in Fig. 8. The loss factor of Al-alloy is the lowest, but the loss factors of AIMCs increase with increasing graphite. The loss factor at the mode ω is the highest of the three modes. It is found that the damping property of AIMC is affected by the amount of graphite particles. Interestingly, the result indicates that the amount of graphite in Al-10%SiC_p-10%C_p is two times greater than that in Al-10%SiC_p-4%C_p, but the loss factor of Al-10%SiC_p-10%C_p does not increase as much as reported by Rohatgi et al. [4].

Fig. 8. Loss factors for Al-alloy, Mn-Cu alloy, Al-10%SiC_p-4%C_p and Al-10%SiC_p-10%C_p at each oscillation mode.

They reported that the damping capacity increases linearly as the incorporated graphite particles increase. The non-linear increase of loss factors can be attributed to the formation of Al₃Ni. Nickel coated on the surface of graphite is dissolved in the matrix and the dissolved nickel exists as aluminum nickel precipitate, Al₃Ni. Al₃Ni is brittle compound and may contribute to reducing the damping capacity. Such the effect of Al₃Ni is more considerable in the AIMCs reinforced with 20%SiC particles. The loss factors of Al-20%SiC_p-0%C_p and Al-20%SiC_p-4%C_p are shown in Fig. 9. The loss factors of both Al-20%SiC_p-0%C_p and Al-20%SiC_p-4%C_p are higher than that of Al-alloy. However, when nickel-coated graphite particles were incorporated into Al-20%SiC_p-0%C_p, the loss factor decreases. It can be concluded that the nickel coated on the surface of graphite is precipitated with the Al-alloy matrix and transforms to the Al₃Ni. The Al₃Ni decrease the amount of Al-alloy matrix that can generate dislocation compared to Al-20%SiC_p-0%C_p and it also surpasses the intrinsic damping of graphite particle

incorporated.

Fig. 9. Loss factors for Al-alloy, Mn-Cu alloy, Al-20%SiC_p-0%C_p and Al-20%SiC_p-4%C_p at each oscillation mode.

4. Effect of heat treatment on damping

The damping capacity was investigated after T6 and the result is shown in Fig. 10. After T6, the loss factor was increased significantly. The increased damping is attributed to the increase of dislocation. Rohatgi et al. reported that heat-treatment increases the dislocation density. Dislocation is closely related to damping property as mentioned above. Tan et al. investigated the aging effect on the damping of an Al-Si alloy matrix composite system [8]. They reported that the damping capacity was increased after aging because discontinuous Si precipitates were coarser during aging. The coarser precipitates reduce a pinning effect and result in an increase of the damping capacity. Also, Kinra et al. reported that heat-treatment increases the grain size and the dislocation density, which contribute to increasing the damping capacity.

Fig. 10. Loss factors for Al-10%SiC_p-4%C_p at each vibration mode after as-casted and T6.

CONCLUSIONS

The damping capacity of Al-alloy, Mn-Cu alloy and Al-Si aluminum alloys reinforced with SiC and nickel-coated graphite particles at various contents has been studied. Their mechanical property and microstructure were also investigated.

1. Graphite and SiC particles are distributed uniformly. The nickel coated on the surface of graphite is precipitated with aluminum and transforms to Al_3Ni .
2. The tensile strength of AIMCs is higher than that of Al-alloy but the elongation is lower due to the brittle SiC and ductile graphite particle incorporation.
3. The damping capacity of AIMCs reinforced with 10% SiC was higher than that of AIMCs reinforced with 20% SiC. In the AIMCs reinforced with 10%SiC, the loss factor is proportionally increased with the amount of graphite particles. In the AIMCs reinforced with 20%SiC, the loss factor is decreased as nickel coated graphite particles were incorporated. It can be attributed to the nickel aluminum precipitate, Al_3Ni , which decreases the amount of Al-alloy matrix, which can generate dislocation. Al_3Ni also surpasses the intrinsic damping property of graphite particle incorporated.
4. After T6, the loss factor was increased significantly. The increased loss factor can attributed to the increase of dislocation density, grain boundary and coarsening of Al-Si precipitate.

REFERENCES

1. M. K. Aghajanian, C. A. Andersson, R. J. Wlener, and B. R. Rossing, "High Reinforcement content Metal Matrix Composites for Automotive Applications", SAE Technical Paper Series 950263, International Congress and Exposition Detroit, Michigan, Feb, 27 – Mar. 2, p1, 1995.
2. S. Boulton and R. Whitaker, "Performance Characteristics of Al MMC Rotor Materials", SAE Technical Paper Series 973025, International Congress and Exposition Detroit, Michigan, Feb, 27 – Mar. 2, p63, 1995.
3. P. K. Rohatgi, D. Nath, S. S. Singh and B. N. Keshavaram, "Factors affecting the damping capacity of cast aluminum-matrix composites", *J. Mater. Sci.*, **29**, 5975.(1994).
4. J. Zhang, R. J. Perez, and E. J. Lavernia, "Dislocation-Induced Damping in Metal Matrix Composites", *J. Mater. Sci.*, **28**, 835. (1993).
5. P. K. Rohatgi, R. Asthana, and A. Kumar, "Damping Capacity of Aluminum Alloy Matrix Composites", Conference Proceedings of the 1988 World Materials Congress, p375, 1988.
6. W. Wu and J. Beech, "The Production of Aluminum-Graphite Particle Composites by Using the Full Mold Process", *The Foundryman*, Feb., p83, 1990.
7. S. W. Ip, R. Sridhar, J. M. Toguri, T. F. Stephenson, and A. E. M. Warner, "Wettability of Nickel Coated Graphite by Aluminum", *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, **A244**, 31.(1998).
8. M. Tan and L. Liou, "Effect of Precipitation on Internal Friction of Rapidly Solidified Al-Si Alloys", *Mater. Sci. Eng.*, **A114**, 205.(1989).